

A Bibliometric Mapping of the Macro-Economic Disruptions of COVID-19

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in a significant crisis for the global economy. Considerable research has been conducted to analyse the subsequent effects of the pandemic on the global environment. The objective of this study is to examine the changing research domains and scientific trends through a retrospective bibliometric analysis of secondary data. Data used in the present study was extracted using the Scopus and Web of Science database. A bibliometric analysis has been conducted, employing multiple indicators, in order to capture the predominant patterns and subjects of research pertaining to the global economy. The process of mapping bibliographic data is conducted through the utilisation of VOSviewer, a software tool, as well as machine learning software. This study identifies and discusses nine key research themes pertaining to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the global economy. Future research directions for researchers, government bodies, central banks, and policymakers have also been proposed.

Key Words: COVID 19, Macroeconomic Impact, Economic Crisis, Global Economy, Bibliometric,

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 Pandemic, though essentially a health crisis, has dented the global economies in a big way (Naseer, 2023; Chetty et.al., 2024). The virus has caused extensive morbidity and mortality globally (Farsalinos et al., 2021). According to Worldometer statistics, 628,451,221 confirmed COVID cases have been reported from 228 countries worldwide. The total number of deaths recorded is 6,412,456. In an attempt to check the exponential spread of the virus, countries enforced tight restrictions on movements by imposing lockdowns, closure of domestic and international borders, and social distancing measures (Alshater et al., 2021). Measures like isolating COVID-positive patients, imposing quarantine, and tracing contacts put tremendous pressure on health infrastructure (Shang et al., 2021). People were confined to their homes, and workplace closures for all economic activities which required physical presence were imposed (Bairoliya & İmrohoroglu, 2023). These measures saved lives, but the consequent reduced economic activity imposed high costs(Thunström et al., 2020, Rathnayaka et al., 2023).

The pandemic's global financial and economic crisis unfolded large-scale uncertainties and insecurity (Leach et al., 2021). The magnitude of the shock and intensity of the damage caused to the economies varied across countries (Altig et al., 2020, Walmsley et al., 2023). The speed and strength of the recovery were dependent on economic resilience and the capacity of countries to implement fiscal measures(Jenny, 2020, Kanupriya 2020).

These measures had far-reaching repercussions which endangered economic health of countries globally (Hashemi et al., 2022). According to the World Economic Outlook Report of IMF published in April 2021, there was a severe 3.5% contraction in the global economy in 2020 (Yeyati & Filippini, 2021). Practically all the countries posted negative growth in 2020. However, due to the series of fiscal and monetary policy measures implemented by countries' governments, the global economic downturn of 2020 was not as severe as initially projected (Jackson, 2021). While the second quarter of the calendar year 2020 witnessed a sharp plunge in the economic growth of most countries, economies were seeing a rebound in the third quarter. In its World Economic Outlook report October 2021, IMF stated that while the World economy had faced a contraction of 3.1%, advanced economies contracted at 4.5%, and emerging markets and developing economies witnessed a contraction of 2.1% in

2020 (International Monetary Fund, October 2021). With Covid cases abating, the World economy grew at 6.1% in 2021, while advanced and emerging economies saw a growth rate of 5.2% and 6.8%, respectively.

Due to the pandemic, labor markets worldwide saw massive disruptions in 2020. As per estimates of (ILO, January 2021), 2020 witnessed a loss of 8.8% of global working hours relative to the fourth quarter of 2019, which is equivalent to 255 million full-time jobs. Countries such as Latin America, the Caribbean, Southern Asia, and Southern Europe were impacted due to the virus and suffered high working-hour losses. Relative to the global financial crisis of 2009, working-hour losses in 2020 were approximately four times greater, with employment losses being 5% higher for women than men and 8.7% higher for young workers than older workers. As per World Bank, ILO estimates that the female labor force participation rate in 2019, which was 48%, declined to 46% in 2020.

The lockdown and health fears triggered an adverse impact on consumer spending and led to a consumption shock. Countries such as China, the United Kingdom, United States faced a consumption change of (-5%), (-6%), and (-1%) in demand for goods, while in the services industry which faced the major brunt of the epidemic, consumption changes was (-12%), (-19%) and (-10%) respectively (McKinsey Global Institute, March 2021).

According to the World Bank's Global Economic Prospect Report published in January 2022, there are growing uncertainties of economic slowdown in the global economy after the strong recovery in 2021. There is an anticipated fear of decelerated global growth from 5.5 percent in 2021 to 4.1 percent in 2022 and 3.2 percent in 2023. The probable reason for this could be the dissipation of pent-up demand and the easing of fiscal and monetary support by countries' governments. The threats of Covid variants, increasing inflation and debt, could imperil the economic resilience of both developed and developing countries. While on withdrawal of quantitative easing, Central Banks globally have been preparing for a soft landing ie on increasing interest rates just enough to stop an economy from facing high inflationary trends without causing a severe downturn or recession, the macroeconomic reality that might pan out, might not be so.

Keeping in mind the havoc caused by the pandemic, researchers post-March 2020 have been analyzing the economic consequences of the health crisis on countries worldwide. Detailed bibliometric analysis of the topics that academicians and economists have

researched during this phase could provide a bird's eye view of the extant research conducted by economists and analysts post-Covid 19.

The present study intends to capture the evolving research domains and scientific trends by doing a bibliometric analysis of secondary data and therefore is retrospective in nature. It brings out the research landscape/ trends related to the impact of COVID-19 on the global economy by analyzing the research articles related to this theme in leading journals. The study seeks to address the following:

- a. Dominant areas of research on the impact of COVID-19 on the Global Economy
- b. Identify propositions to guide future research in this domain

Knowledge discovery in databases (KDD) text mining for the meta-trend analysis of textual data has been used on the compendium of abstracts related to research undertaken in the economics domain post-Covid 19 pandemic. The present bibliometric study uses the text mining technique and employs the LDA algorithm in case of analysis through Topic Modeling and Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA). LDA and LSA were applied to the abstracts to identify the cognitive structures within the data.

2. Methodology

Bibliometrics can be regarded as a field of research in which the researchers apply mathematical and statistical tools to analyze the publishing patterns within the published data (Donthu et al., 2021; McCain, 1996). Bibliometric studies decipher research topics evolving in the knowledge landscape related to a particular field and its holistic development over time (Durieux & Gevenois, 2010; Rey-Martí et al., 2016). Quantitative and objective tools are applied for organizing data within the field to bring out critical data-driven insights in the particular research domain and relationships at the micro level (G. Chen & Xiao, 2016).

Fig 1 depicts the research design of the present study. In the initial stage, the Scopus and Web of Science databases were used to identify the relevant research studies focusing on the economic impact of COVID19. Next, a performance analysis of the compendium of abstracts was done to determine the most cited studies and publication period. This was followed by science mapping of the data using Co-word Analysis using Text mining and VOSviewer Software.

Figure 1: Research design for the bibliometric study

A qualitative approach was used to capture deeper meanings from the compendium of abstracts of research manuscripts published from May 2020- September 2022. The onset dates of the pandemic and the publication of research articles assessing its impact on the global economy were considered to select the abstracts. Abstracts of manuscripts were used for text mining as they provide the essence of the research and help lessen the data noise in the investigation. The dataset was the compendium of abstracts from 385 refereed journal manuscripts from databases such as Taylor and Francis, Elsevier, Springer, Wiley, and Sage. In order to retrieve all relevant research studies, the keyword search included titles, abstracts, and keywords. In order to retrieve relevant abstracts, the keywords search for "COVID 19", "novel coronavirus 2019 + economy", "2019-nCoV + Global Economy", "novel coronavirus + world economy", "SARS-CoV-2 + global economy", "Coronavirus Disease 2019 + global economy", "COVID 19 + world economy", "novel coronavirus 2019 + world economy" were used. In the initial search, a total of 939 articles were found. The result was refined to include research articles in economics that were published in peer-reviewed journals and 447 articles were identified. After removing duplicates, a performance analysis of the 385 shortlisted articles was done.

Machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) are used for data mining and identifying text patterns (Jelodar et al., 2018). Data analysis involved automated information extraction from an unstructured text dataset. The text mining technique was used (Gupta & Misra, 2023). Since the text mining dataset is primarily unstructured, data noisiness was cleaned from the dataset using R-Programming (R) statistical Software. Additionally, VOSviewer software was also used for co-word analysis. The consequent co-word networks of keywords were created that were classified into clusters. These clusters were then examined to decipher the pertinent themes derived from the literature. The two researchers separately interpreted the clusters of abstracts that were formed using unsupervised machine learning to ensure inter-rater reliability (Gwet, 2014). Similarly, the themes were derived by labeling the clusters.

3. Performance Analysis

In order to identify the trends in publication and their impact, a performance analysis of the abstracts was done. The compendium of abstracts was classified based on the publication period and most cited articles.

3.1 Publication Growth Analysis

The publication growth trends reflect the progression in the publication of research articles analyzing the economic impact of the pandemic since its start. The data has been depicted monthly to understand the developments better (Fig: 2).

Fig 2: Growth Trend of Research Publications

3.2 Most Cited articles

The most cited research papers on the impact of the pandemic on global economy have been listed in Table: 1. Noticeably, these papers bring forth the various facets of the economic impact.

Table 1: Most Cited Papers on the Economic Impact of the Pandemic

Rank	Title of Research Paper	Citation (as on 10 th October 2022)
1.	The Macroeconomics of Epidemics	1509
2.	Corporate immunity to the COVID-19 Pandemic	702
3.	Longer-Run Economic Consequences of Pandemics	664
4.	Supply and demand shocks in the COVID-19 Pandemic: industry and occupation perspective	519
5.	A critical analysis of the impacts of COVID-19 on the global economy and ecosystems and opportunities for circular economy strategies	436
6.	Coronavirus Perceptions and Economic Anxiety	403
7.	Can supply chain risk management practices mitigate the disruption impacts on supply chains' resilience and robustness? Evidence from an empirical survey in a COVID-19 outbreak era	284
8.	Macroeconomic Dynamics and Reallocation in an Epidemic: Evaluating the "Swedish Solution"	251
9.	When Selling Becomes Viral: Disruptions in Debt Markets in the COVID-19 Crisis and the Fed's Response	246
10.	Coronavirus Fears and Macroeconomic Expectations	222

4.Data Analysis

4.1 Data Mining

Topic Modeling of the themes and topics for an in-depth investigation of the abstracts was done (Gurcan & Cagiltay, 2019). Two models, Topic Modeling, and LSA (Latent Semantic Analysis), were used for data analysis. NLP identified the tentative topics through Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA). The model helps identify the text's most influential/frequently used words. Subsequently, co-word networks were used to generate clusters using the VOSviewer Software. The data from the two was collated to identify underlying themes from the data and label the topics representative of the text (Buenaño-Fernandez et al., 2020).

4.2.1 Topic Modelling

To identify the key themes that depict the research themes prevalent in the abstracts mined, topic modelling analysis was done. The extant literature extracted nine meaningful research topics, and their corresponding top words are described in Table 2. Also, using the

VOSviewer Software, co-word networks were used to generate clusters of research themes (Fig 3). This facilitated the triangulation of themes extracted.

Fig 3: Co-word Network of Research Themes

Table 2: Dominant topics in research on COVID-19 and its impact on the Global Economy

Topic Modelling		Vosviewer		Theme Deduction	Exemplary Studies
Topic No.	Key Words	Colour	Key Words		
1.	economic, policy, market, crisis, lockdown, stock, government, trade, growth, financial	Red	Stock return, volatility, oil, proxy, variable Positive effect, trading volume	COVID-19 and financial markets	(Feng et al., 2021),(Yao et al., 2021),(Nguyen et al., 2021), (Ngo & Nguyen, 2022)
2.	India, migrant, rural, urban, lockdown, labor, vulnerability	Yellow	Worker, rural area, urban area, income loss, India	Impact of Covid on Migrant Workers in India	(Jha & Jha, 2020), (Misra & Gupta, 2021), (Jha & Kumar, 2020), (Behera et al., 2021),

3.	health, public, cases, employment, measures, world, conditions	Dark Blue	infection, death, testing, condition	COVID-19 and Public Health Conditions	(Liao et al., 2021),(Kim & Loayza, 2022),(Segarra-Blasco et al., 2021)
4.	Stimulus, income, institutions, widespread, globe, burden, institutions, west, trajectory	Light Blue	the remittance, exchange rate, payment, host country, public policy, negative impact	Policy Responses to COVID 19	(Makin & Layton, 2021), (Thakur & Kumar, 2021), (Kumar, 2020), (Harjoto et al., 2021)
5.	Countries, workers, sectors, household, firms, negative, models, rates, returns, data, higher, significantly	Mauve	Firm, investment, disruption, enterprise, value, lockdown measure	Sector-Specific Impact of COVID 19	(Darougheh, 2021), (Ando & Hayakawa, 2022), (Chen et al., 2022),
6.	Food, supply chain, resilient, risks, emergency, deaths, safety, sustainability	Purple	Supply chain, food security, recession, scenario, output, demand shock	Global Supply Chain Disruptions	(Zhang, 2021),(Ayadi et al., 2022), (Bekkers & Koopman, 2022), (Hitt et al., 2021)
7.	Exports, African, globalization, productivity, job, medical, deaths, FDI, exchange	Green	Inequality, poverty, household, education, Ghana	Socio-Economic Impacts of COVID-19 in Africa	(Chitiga-Mabugu et al., 2021), (Adam et al., 2020), (Burger & Calitz, 2021)
8.	European, consumption, behavior, inflation, labor, fiscal, closures, estimates, remittances	Orange	Goods, trade, China, import, employment, distress, France	Impact of COVID on Countries	(Baert, 2021), (Zamfir & Iordache, 2022), (Azimli, 2022), (Mueller-Langer & Gomez-Herrera, 2022)
9.	Social, cash, financial, econometric, regression, expansion, contrast, citizens	--	--	Econometric analysis of the impact of COVID 19	(Zhang et al., 2021), (Zhao et al., 2021), (Ngo et al., 2022), (Chen et al., 2021)

Topic 1 covers financial markets and COVID-19. Lockdowns produced a financial market liquidity crisis and asset undervaluation (Goldstein et al., 2021). Global stock market indexes plummeted (Yao et al., 2021, Mundi. & Yadav 2023, Salman & Ali., 2024). After

stimulus measures, global financial markets recovered fast (Ngo & Nguyen, 2022, Gupta, H. et al., 2022). The worldwide academic community has conducted amazing study to explain the phenomenon, such as "Impacts of COVID-19 on financial markets: from the perspective of financial stress" and "The foreign investors' behaviours during the pandemic in emerging market."

Topic 2 examines COVID-19's effects on 'Migrant Workers in India.' Research focused on migrant workers' psychosocial difficulties. The researchers examined 'Labour in India and the COVID-19 Pandemic' and 'COVID-19 Crisis and Some Contours of the Rural Labour Market in India'. The mental, financial, and emotional agony of migrant workers owing to substantial reverse migration caused a huge socio-economic catastrophe in India (Behera et al., 2021; P. Jha & Kumar, 2020; Misra & Gupta, 2021). The downturn caused job losses, labour migration, demand-supply gaps, supply chain disruptions, and GDP decline (Rana & Haque, 2020, Kujur & Goswami, 2022, Prusty et al., 2022).

Topic 3 study included "COVID-19 and Public Health Conditions." The research examined 'COVID-19 and women's health: Examining changes in mental health and fertility' and 'Social-economic consequences of COVID-19 epidemic in India'. COVID 19 was designated a Public Health Emergency of International Concern by the World Health Organisation (WHO) on January 30, 2020 (Team, 2020). The healthcare infrastructure struggled to treat, diagnose, trace, and quarantine affected people and their contacts. The pandemic prompted mental health difficulties to surface (Adams-Prassl et al., 2022, Warriar et al., 2021).

Topic 4 is related to 'Policy Responses to COVID-19/ Economic Stimulus and relief'. To mitigate the damage caused by the pandemic to the economy, the governments and Central Banks of countries globally announced substantial and unprecedented fiscal and monetary stimulus measures to cope with the crisis (Rana, 2020, Makin & Layton, 2021,). The Central Governments managed the fiscal policy interventions, such as tax relief, sector-specific support, employment, etc. '*The global fiscal response to COVID-19: Risks and repercussions*' and '*Macroeconomic Consequences of a Lockdown and Its Policy Implications*', are some such studies.

Topic 5 covers COVID-19's sector-specific effects. The epidemic had varying effects on different economic sectors, according to research. Tourism, hotels, and aviation suffered (Ando & Hayakawa, 2022). Production companies that required physical touch had to close (Donthu & Gustafsson, 2020). IT, education, and other businesses that could use remote working with technical assistance had little influence (Rana et al., 2020, Gupta & Garg, 2021). The epidemic first hampered the healthcare industry (Nagurney, 2021, Rana, 2021). 'The Importance of Agriculture in the Economy: Impacts from COVID-19' and 'COVID-19 and tourism: What can we learn from the past' were notable research.

Topic 6 deals with 'Global Supply Chain Disruptions.' The pandemic has aggravated the vulnerabilities of logistic systems and the global supply chain (AlNemer, 2023; Donthu & Gustafsson, 2020). The lockdowns imposed to curb the pandemic stopped or slowed manufacturing since raw materials, inputs and final product availability were impacted (Rana, 2022). Well-known scholarly works include, '*Optimization of supply chain networks with the inclusion of labor: Applications to COVID-19 pandemic disruptions*', and '*Supply chain recovery challenges in the wake of COVID-19 pandemic*'.

Topic 7 is "COVID-19's Socio-Economic Impact in Africa." African countries have been hit harder by the epidemic than industrialised nations (Cabore et al., 2022). The dread of profound despair follows (Mashige et al., 2021). The continent's demographic, economic, and healthcare amenities differ each country, hence the influence does too. The virus must be fought with starvation, hunger, and pneumonia. The works 'Fiscal expenditures, revenues and labour productivity in South Africa' and 'Analysing the final impact of COVID-19 in Africa' are notable.

The "Impact of COVID on Countries" is Topic 8. 'The evolution of European economic institutions during the COVID-19 crisis', 'Black swan events and COVID-19 outbreak: Sector level evidence from the US, UK, and European stock markets', and 'Mobility restrictions and the substitution between on-site and remote work: Empirical evidence from a European online labour market' are examples. The pandemic's socio-economic impact has been widespread across Europe. Germany, Spain, France, and Italy are among the most affected (Capello & Caragliu, 2021). Many academic research papers have examined the pandemic's impact and recovery in the EU.

'Econometric analysis of COVID-19' is Topic 9. Econometrics analyses economic phenomena using mathematical and statistical methods (Jain et al., 2021). Policymakers can use the inference to make better decisions (Jiang et al., 2020). To estimate and forecast the efficacy of different viral control strategies, the pattern of virus transmission and dissemination, pandemic fatalities, recovery, etc. must be analysed (Alvarez & Kreinovich, 2020). 'The impacts of covid-19 pandemic on macroeconomic indicators for European nations' and 'Economic policy uncertainty and China's growth-at-risk' are examples.

4.2.2 Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA):

LSA was applied to the abstracts to identify the cognitive structures within the data by performing spatial and statistical analysis on the corpus of data (Dumais et al., 1988; Evangelopoulos, 2011). Contextual similarity can thus be construed to identify meaningful thematic structures (Kwon et al., 2017).

Table 3: Results of Scenario and Highest Loading Terms

Number	Scenario/ Topic	Highest Loading Terms
1.	Migrant Workers	Asia, contractual, urban, Bihar, Maharashtra, organized, construction, informal.
2.	Health	System, world, strategy, structural, women, prices, movement, negatively.
3.	Income	reducing, discretionary, welfare, expenditure, medical, society
4.	Stimulus	Middle income, combat, priorities, exposed, seasonal, providing, July
5.	Lockdown	shutdown, reverse, rural, wages, structural, lives, world, vulnerability
6.	Growth rate	long-term, home, shock, wage, mobility, unemployment, China, development, cases
7.	Supply chain	resilient, disease, trust, challenge, microfinance, immigration, infections
8.	Inflation	prices, disruptions, package, lives, testing, structural, health, agriculture, world
9.	Financial Markets	Economic, risk, policy, crisis, volatility, efficiency, disaster, Asian, Pandemic, Spill-over, fiscal, shocks,
10.	Consumption behaviour	European, Japanese, investment, restriction, firms, macro-economy, inflation, sectoral
11.	Globalization	WFH, FDI, threat, layoffs, linkages, procurement

LSA has identified eleven significant discourses (Table 3 above).

Scenario 1: Migrant Workers. Migrant workers have been worst hit by the epidemic (Behera et al., 2021; Walmsley et al., 2021). They were the first to feel the economic blow, stranded in metropolitan centres, jobless, and driven to flee (Roy & Bose, 2021). After India's 2020 shutdown, migrant labourers reversed migration in large numbers. Since COVID-19 limitations began in Thailand, the Migrant Working Group predicted in June 2020 that 700,000 migrant workers had lost their employment. Over 50% of Malaysian textile and clothing industries closed, leaving thousands unemployed (Loone, 2020a; 2002b). In Sri Lanka, migrant labourers suffered extraordinary employment losses (Jones, Mudaliar, & Piper, 2021).

Scenario 2: Health. The pandemic, essentially a significant health crisis, disrupted healthcare systems globally. The USA spends over 16% of its total GDP; Japan, Canada, Germany, etc., spend over 10% of its GDP on healthcare. In FY 2020-21, India spent 1.8% of its GDP on healthcare. People were compelled to be confined to their homes and adhere to the health advisories regarding the use of masks, sanitizers, social distancing, etc. The lacunae, even in the robust healthcare systems of developed nations, were exposed. Social distancing strategies countries adopt to curb the spread of the virus have negatively impacted the socio-economic structures (Nwosu et al., 2022). This also exposed the gender-regressive scenario prevalent worldwide. Women workers face numerous challenges like unemployment, elderly care, childcare responsibility, children, and reduced income (Neetha, 2021).

Scenario 3: Income. The pandemic severely impacted the world of work (Milovanska-Farrington, 2022). Lockdown and social distancing norms resulted in business closures and reduced scale of operations. The consequent financial and economic shock resulted in widespread job losses and income inequality (O'Keeffe & Papadopoulos, 2021). According to a report, Covid 19 widened wealth gaps globally, resulting in the world's richest 10% owning 76% of the global wealth. Economic inequality levels are aggravated in developing regions (home to approximately two-thirds of the world's poor). (WEF, April 2022) stated that the discretionary expenditure was significantly reduced, and people were holding money to spend on out-of-pocket medical/ health care expenses.

Scenario 4: Stimulus. To combat the economic loss precipitated by the pandemic, stimulus packages were released by the governments of various countries (Hürtgen, 2021). Fiscal and monetary policy measures were introduced to stimulate the economies out of the recession (Ray & Kumar, 2021). To increase employment, investment, and economic demand, measures like lower interest rates and taxes, financial assistance, etc., were provided. % Share of GDP granted as a fiscal stimulus package to counter the adverse impact of the pandemic was 26.46%, UK 18.07%, India 3.5%, EU 11.27%, Australia 19.97%.

Scenario 5: Lockdown. In order to check the spread of the virus, the lockdown was imposed by a large number of countries. All offices, business units, schools, commercial activities, etc., were shut down to prevent social interactions. This unprecedented lockdown and subsequent extensions caused severe disruptions to the economy resulting in demand and supply disruptions (Mehrotra & Parida, 2021). The closure of factories in cities exposed the vulnerability of rural migrants as they were compelled to reverse migrate to their native villages (Jha & Kumar, 2020).

Scenario 6: Growth Rate. The growth rate of global economies has been badly hit by the pandemic, which originated in China (Augustin et al., 2022). Consequent lockdowns imposed by governments to curb the number of cases resulted in substantial economic shock. Unemployment and job losses were extensive since business activities were put on hold (O’Keeffe & Papadopoulos, 2021). Ramifications would be felt in the long-term economic sentiments (Harjoto et al., 2021).

Scenario 7: Supply Chain. The pandemic is a classic example of a high-impact-low-probability (HILP) event (Mont et al., 2021). It has challenged and tested the resilience of the robust supply chains since the availability of raw materials, labor, etc., was adversely impacted (Verma & Gustafsson, 2020). Fear of infections and disease disrupted the manufacturing industries. Though immigration is an effective way to check labor shortages, there is a labor shortage to fill the vacant positions, even in developed economies (Borjas & Cassidy, 2020).

Scenario 8: Inflation. One of the most tangible outcomes of the pandemic on the world economy has been its impact on inflation (Apergis & Apergis, 2021). As the countries re-opened their economies, the recovery in economic activity and excess liquidity in the financial flow of countries led to increasing global inflation. The stimulus package spending and increased consumer spending due to pent-up demand further increased inflation (Bresser-

Pereira, 2020). Further, rising crude prices, energy, food prices, and supply chain disruptions aggravated the situation (Armantier et al., 2021). While the world was still recovering from the economic upheaval caused due to the virus and had just started tightening liquidity conditions and reducing money supply to counter inflationary pressures, the Russia-Ukraine war added fuel to the inflationary fire. IMF, in its July 2022 WEO update, revised the inflation levels estimate for 2022-23 to 6.6% in advanced economies and 9.5% in emerging markets and developing economies (IMF, July 2022).

Scenario 9: Financial Markets. Global financial markets witnessed unprecedented volatility and uncertainty (Ganie et al., 2022). The stock, bonds, and commodity markets (including crude oil and gold) were characterized by drastic movements. Economic activities were paralyzed by the lockdowns imposed by countries to check the spread of disease (Bouri et al., 2022). The oil and stock prices plunged sharply with the onset of this crisis (Mensi et al., 2022). The US, UK, and Asian markets were all disrupted since the magnitude of financial loss was enormous (Goldstein et al., 2021). The markets responded quite favorably to the monetary and fiscal measures adopted by governments to stimulate economic recovery (Makin & Layton, 2021).

Scenario 10: Consumption Behavior. The pandemic has dramatically impacted the consumption psychology and behavior of people. Analysis of economic data reveals that the pandemic manifested a significant shift in consumption behavior, influencing what and how they buy. Consumer purchase was limited to essential/ necessity items like food, health, and hygiene (Crosta et al., 2021). Restrictions on movements facilitated online shopping, non-contact delivery, and digital payments as the new normal (Xiong et al., 2021). With negligible discretionary expenditure being incurred, firms engaged in tourism, recreation, travel and such sectors suffered adversely.

Scenario 11: Globalization. Global interconnectedness has been regarded as one of the potential causes for the virus's global spread since international movements of people caused human interactions (Shrestha et al., 2020). As the cross-border economic activities between countries were disturbed, trade and investment flow were disrupted. These hurt the FDI of multinational corporations, the key elements of global value chains (Ando & Hayakawa, 2022). The health crisis has been responsible for a significant socio-economic crisis, as many firms across sectors have been compelled to lay off employees (Tu et al.,

2021). This crisis has changed the talent procurement norms and opened the opportunity for smart working and collaborative spaces (Hu, 2020).

Future Research Directions:

The topics derived by LSA were classified into three broad categories; Country specific impact, Global impact, and country and global impact of the pandemic. Upon analysis, it was observed that the economic impact of COVID has been localized and country-specific (Fig 4). For instance, countries' health infrastructure varies; therefore, the severity of the impact of the pandemic differed across countries. Further, specific themes focus on global impact, for instance, supply chain disruptions, which was essentially a global phenomenon on account of the international inter-connectedness of countries have also evolved. Also, some themes overlap with the country-specific and global impact of the pandemic ie Glocal impact, the GDP growth rate/ recovery rates of countries, for instance have also been identified. Accordingly, the way forward / future research directions have been proposed by the researchers (Table 4).

Figure 4: Economic Impact of COVID 19

Table 4: Future Research Directions**Country-Specific Impact****Health:**

Proposition 1: Strategies to improve health infrastructure in developed and less developed economies?

Proposition 2: The Pandemic has brought to the forefront health inequalities. Strategies to be devised for mitigating health inequalities.

Stimulus:

Proposition 1: Estimate the effectiveness of the monetary and fiscal stimulus measures implemented to mitigate the damage caused by the Pandemic.

Proposition 2: To estimate the impact of tightening monetary flow to ensure a soft landing in developed and emerging economies.

Migrant Workers:

Proposition 1: Major reforms in labor management by policymakers and corporates are mandatory to reduce the vulnerability of workers.

Proposition 2: Assessing the impact and strategies to overcome the negative effect of the Pandemic on the labor market in developing economies.

Lockdown:

Proposition 1: Strategies to impose physical contact restriction policies such as lockdown to minimize its economic impact?

Proposition 2: Estimating the impact of lockdown on sectors/industries.

Glocal**Consumption:**

Proposition 1: Identifying strategies for increasing consumer confidence and business sentiments needs to be devised.

Proposition 2: Strategies and avenues explored by corporations to increase people's consumption behavior.

Income:

Proposition 1: Estimating the root cause of the aggravated income inequality post-Pandemic.

Proposition 2: Studies to ascertain the macroeconomic resilience of countries during a downturn.

Growth Rate:

Proposition 1: Strategies to increase GDP growth rate post the Pandemic.

Proposition 2: Strategies to balance GDP growth and inflationary pressures in the post-pandemic phase.

Inflation:

Proposition 1: Roadmap to counter inflation and ensure economies do not fall into recession.

Proposition 2: Assess the strategies to check inflation, keeping the geopolitical scenario in mind.

Global Impact**Supply Chain**

Proposition 1: Assessing the supply chain challenges and possible mitigation strategies across various industries in the post-pandemic phase.

Proposition 2: Identifying suitable strategies to minimize losses due to disruptions in the supply chain due to global pandemics.

Proposition 3• What policies should companies devise for reshoring of supply chain and shifting to dual sourcing?

Financial Markets:

Proposition 1: Economic resilience to reduce stock market volatility needs to be deciphered.

Proposition 2: The impact of the lockdown on sectors/industries and its consequent impact on stock markets need to be understood.

Globalization:

Proposition 1: Strategies for implementing friend-shoring options to preserve the continuity of supplies.

Proposition 2: The inter and intra-country inequalities have increased post the Pandemic, which could increase anti-globalization opinions. Studies could be undertaken to assess these phenomena.

Conclusion:

From a compendium of 385 articles that analyzed the pandemic's economic impact across the globe, the present study explored the academic research in this domain to identify the most prominent research themes and possible future research propositions. Nine major research themes ie. COVID-19 and financial markets, Impact of Covid on Migrant Workers in India, COVID-19 and Public Health Conditions, Policy Responses to COVID 19, Sector-Specific Impact of COVID 19, Global Supply Chain Disruptions, Socio-Economic Impacts of COVID-19 in Africa, Impact of COVID on Countries and Econometric analysis of the impact of COVID 19 have emerged upon a content analysis of the extant literature. After categorizing the themes into impact at the country-specific and global levels and overlap amongst the two, future research propositions have been offered.

Additionally, future research can also study the economic impact of large-scale disruptions at the international level due to the geopolitical tensions, an outcome of the ongoing Russia-Ukraine war since February 2022. The major limitation of this paper is the inclusion of only Scopus and Web of Science database journal articles. Though it is comprehensive, other databases, such as Google Scholar, Ebsco, UGC Care, non-indexed, etc., could have been included. Further, studies included represent existing research (published and in-press articles); however, ongoing and unpublished knowledge, such as articles under review, have not been included.

Conflict of Interests:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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